

HOW SOCIAL MEDIA DRIVES A THIRD WORLD COUNTRY'S CONSUMER PURCHASE ACTION: A CASE STUDY OF PAKISTAN

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Abstract

The research examined the effect of social media marketing factors (SMMF) on the purchase intention (PI) of fashion brands in Pakistan with trust (TR), brand awareness (BA), perceived value (PV) and entertainment (ENT) as mediators. Based on the SOR theory, it used quantitative, explicative study in order to investigate the complex interactions among these constructs. This questionnaire was structured by the Likert scale questionnaire for Pakistani fashion brands, and 214 responses were analyzed through PLS-SEM to evaluate structural and measurement models. The result indicated that BA, ENT, PV have a positive and significant effect on PI. Additionally, SMMF has a positive and significant effect on BA, ENT, PV and TR. In addition, TR has a positive and significant effect on PI. TR mediates SMMF and PI positively but insignificantly, while PV, ENT, and BA mediate positively and significantly. Thus, fashion brand managers in Pakistan should boost social media engagement to enhance awareness, trust, and loyalty.

INTRODUCTION

Social media is becoming a growing part of Pakistan's fashion industry, connecting people and brands differently. In the present, fashion comes in the form of everyday life, as the platforms such as Instagram, Facebook and TikTok transform casual viewing to inspiration and discovery (Siddiqui et al., 2025). When that trust is built, brand awareness grows naturally as people feel closer and more familiar with specific fashion names. A sense of recognition is a loyalty incentive and makes a brand distinctive from others in the crowd (Taj et al., 2025).

Pakistan's fashion industry is an active and culturally rich industry that showcases exquisite craftsmanship, diverse textiles and modern fashion design (Riaz et al., 2025). On top of that, in recent decades, social media has had a major influence on consumer preferences and purchasing decisions (Arshad et al., 2024).

When buying fashion products, more than 70% of Pakistani consumers would prefer to seek social media advertisements, indicating that interaction with digital media is associated with shopping behavior (Hussain et al., 2024). Consequently, the fashion industry in Pakistan is thriving, steered by cultural pride, digital technology and shopper transformations (Arshad et al., 2024; Riaz et al., 2025).

The problem is that Pakistan's fashion brands find it difficult to translate social media engagement into real purchase intent. The effect on purchase intentions is caused by low consumer trust, brand awareness, perceived value uncertainty, and lack of entertaining or engaging content online (Aziz et al., 2024). Although digital advertising is growing rapidly and social media adoption is high, many fashion brands are not effectively influencing shoppers' purchase intentions. This gap

between web visibility and retail sales reflects challenges in social media marketing effectiveness within Pakistan's fashion industry (Majeed et al., 2024). If unresolved, brands may face eroding customer loyalty, weak sales growth, inefficient marketing expenditures, poor brand equity, and low repurchase intention (Siddiqui et al., 2025). These challenges may hinder long-term economic stability and global competitiveness. Limited research explores how Pakistani consumers buy online in the fashion sector. Therefore, this study investigates social media marketing's influence on purchase intention through trust, brand awareness, perceived value, and entertainment to enhance digital marketing strategies in Pakistan's fashion industry (Lakho & Rashid, 2025).

Previous research has examined the influence of social media marketing on consumer behavior or brand performance. Many countries show that social media is widely used to communicate brand information, enhance customer understanding, and support relationship building. Researchers also agree that social media marketing helps promote brand awareness, trust, and perceived value, while shaping consumers' purchasing intentions (Majeed et al., 2024).

However, several aspects of this relationship remain poorly understood in Pakistan's fashion industry. Existing literature largely focuses on Western or developed markets and fails to address Pakistan's cultural, economic, and technological barriers. Research on consumer willingness to purchase in developing economies is also limited (Lakho & Rashid, 2025). Few studies examine these trends in Pakistan's rapidly growing fashion sector, creating an important gap. Addressing this gap can provide local insights and guide brands in developing relevant, trusted, and engaging social media strategies (Aziz et al., 2024). Therefore, the purpose of the study is to investigate the role of social media marketing on the purchase intention of fashion brands in Pakistan, with trust, brand awareness, perceived value, and entertainment as mediating variables.

This research is significant because it stresses how trust, brand awareness, perceived value, and entertainment are mediated in social

media advertising, shaping how fashion brands in Pakistan connect with customers. As Pakistan's fashion industry rapidly expands, social media has become a necessary marketing tool for advertising products, reaching customers, and shaping consumer preferences (Seema, 2024). The study adds to marketing literature by integrating emotional, cognitive, and relational elements to explain online purchase intentions. It also provides marketers, researchers, and policymakers with insights into digital interactions in emerging markets, bridging theory and practice and supporting sustainable brand growth through social media engagement (Siddiqui et al., 2025).

It has six sections that cover the entire research process in this research. First section of the thesis is a start on the thesis to discuss a background and a description of the research that includes a description of variables, problems and gaps in research, research objective, study's significance and scope and definition of key words. The second section of the literature review provides theoretical background for hypothesis development. The third section will describe research methodology and data analysis techniques. The fourth is data analysis, which includes the research results. The fifth section is the discussion and the last section is conclusion and recommendations will include the end of the study and policy recommendations.

Literature Review

Theoretical Underpinnings

Mehrabian and Russell (1974) proposed the Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) model, which explains how external environmental cues (Stimulus) trigger internal cognitive and emotional states (Organism) that guide behavioral actions (Response). This theory is applicable in explaining how fashion brands use social media marketing to influence consumer decision-making (Zhu et al., 2020). Advertising, influencer content, brand images, product videos, and reviews act as stimuli that provide information and experiences. The organism phase involves internal processing reflected through trust, brand awareness, perceived value, and entertainment (Olfat et al., 2022). Consumers evaluate credibility, recognize benefits, and experience satisfaction

before forming purchase intention, which represents the response. Positive internal states increase the likelihood of positive consumer behavior, explaining how social media marketing indirectly influences purchase intention in online fashion retailing (Sohaib et al., 2022).

Development of the Hypotheses

SMM strategies such as unified brand messaging, interactive content, influencer collaborations, and customer engagement act as external signals shaping consumer perception of a brand. Consumers assess credibility, reliability, and authenticity through these activities, forming trust (Mohamed Sodom et al., 2024). Public interaction on social media, including prompt responses, positive reviews, and informative content, reduces perceived risk and strengthens trust (Ali et al., 2025). Through SMM, trust encourages purchase likelihood, repeat behavior, positive word of mouth, and leads to favorable outcomes such as loyalty and purchase intentions (Jiang & Chen, 2024). Hence, the hypothesis has formed:

H1: SMM has a positive impact on trust.

Zeqiri et al. (2025) indicate that social media marketing strongly influences brand awareness. Platforms such as Instagram, Facebook, TikTok, and YouTube allow brands to deliver engaging content, unified messages, promotions, and interactive campaigns that enhance visibility and recall. Influencers, live stories, user-generated content, and interactive features like polls and shares further strengthen brand identity. Frequent exposure to well-crafted social media content improves brand recall and positive perceptions, making SMM an effective tool for building and sustaining brand awareness in competitive markets (Yum & Kim, 2024). Hence, the hypothesis has formed:

H2: SMM has a positive impact on brand awareness.

SMM enhances perceived value by engaging consumers through storytelling, immersive content, and interactive campaigns that create emotional and functional benefits beyond product features (van Deventer & Saraiva, 2025). It also enables brands to highlight exclusivity, promotions, and limited-time offers, increasing utility and desirability. Peer

interactions and community engagement further strengthen value perceptions, fostering satisfaction and loyalty through enriched consumer experiences driven by social media connections (Yum & Kim, 2024). Hence, the hypothesis has formed:

H3: SMM has a positive impact on perceived value.

SMM and entertainment create engaging and immersive brand experiences through interactive content such as short videos, live sessions, polls, contests, and games on social media platforms (Ali et al., 2025). Entertaining content encourages sharing, strengthens emotional engagement, improves brand recall, and generates positive attitudes, influencing purchase decisions and brand loyalty. By adding entertainment, brands transform routine marketing into experiential engagement, encouraging active consumer participation rather than passive observation (Chen et al., 2024). Hence, the hypothesis has formed:

H4: SMM has a positive impact on the entertainment industry.

Trust strongly influences consumers' purchase intention by reducing perceived risk and increasing confidence in brand reliability, integrity, and promise fulfillment (Mohamed Sodom et al., 2024). Trusted brands are viewed as credible and authentic, encouraging higher purchase intentions. In digital environments, trust is built through consistent communication, positive reviews, influencer endorsements, and responsive service, leading to repeat purchases, loyalty, and the conversion of marketing efforts into actual buying behavior (Yum & Kim, 2024). Hence, the hypothesis has formed:

H5: Trust positively influences purchase intention.

Brand awareness and purchase intention positively and significantly influence consumer behavior (Ismael et al., 2025). Consumers exposed to brand messages are more likely to trust and consider the brand in decision making. High brand awareness enhances visibility, reduces perceived risk, and builds familiarity, making consumers feel secure in purchasing decisions and strengthening acquisition, loyalty, and competitive success in

the market (Zeqiri et al., 2025). Hence, the hypothesis has formed:

H6: Brand awareness positively influences purchase intention.

Perceived value plays a central role in shaping purchase intention by influencing consumers' evaluation of benefits relative to cost, effort, and time (Bevan-Dye, 2024). Higher perceived value increases satisfaction, reduces uncertainty, and strengthens buying confidence. Marketing activities that emphasize quality, utility, and unique advantages enhance perceived value, making products appear more rewarding than alternatives. Thus, perceived value links functional and emotional benefits with consumers' willingness to purchase and is essential for effective marketing outcomes (van Deventer & Saraiva, 2025). Hence, the hypothesis has formed:

H7: Perceived value positively influences purchase intention.

Entertainment positively influences purchase intention by creating engaging and enjoyable brand experiences. Interactive campaigns, videos, gamification, and influencer collaborations generate positive emotions, reduce monotony, and strengthen emotional connections with brands. These experiences foster favorable attitudes, increase content engagement, and encourage consumers to spend more time with brands, ultimately driving purchasing intentions and enhancing overall brand performance (Chen et al., 2024).

Hence, the hypothesis has formed:

H8: Entertainment has a positive impact on purchase intention.

Trust acts as a critical mediator between social media marketing and purchase intention. While SMM increases visibility and interaction, purchasing decisions depend on consumers' internal evaluation of brand trust (Zeqiri et al., 2025). Effective SMM builds confidence, reduces perceived risk, and fosters positive brand attitudes, thereby strengthening purchase intention. Trust forms a psychological link that converts digital engagement into buying behavior and leads to stronger customer engagement and improved sales performance for socially active brands (Jiang & Chen, 2024). Hence, the hypothesis has formed:

H9: Trust positively mediates the impact of SMM on purchase intention.

Brand awareness acts as an important intervening factor between social media marketing and purchase intention. While SMM increases visibility and engagement, consumers' brand experiences shape buying decisions (Ismael et al., 2025). Higher brand awareness helps consumers remember the brand, associate it with positive attributes, and feel confident in choosing it over competitors. Thus, brand awareness serves as a psychological bridge linking social media efforts to consumer engagement, preference, and eventual purchase intention (Zeqiri et al., 2025). Hence, the hypothesis has formed:

H10: Brand awareness positively mediates the impact of SMM on purchase intention.

Perceived value acts as an important mediator between social media marketing and purchase intention. While SMM enhances visibility and interaction, purchasing decisions depend on consumers' evaluation of functional and emotional benefits relative to cost (Bevan-Dye, 2024; Jiang & Chen, 2024). SMM strengthens perceived value through information, demonstrations, personalized experiences, and reviews, improving satisfaction and motivation to purchase. Thus, perceived value serves as a key psychological mechanism linking social media engagement to purchasing behavior (Yum & Kim, 2024). Hence, the hypothesis has formed:

H11: Perceived value positively mediates the impact of SMM on purchase intention.

Entertainment serves as a significant mediator between social media marketing and purchase intention. Fun and emotionally gratifying experiences through content, ads, influencer collaborations, and interactive campaigns enhance brand interaction, making it memorable and satisfying (Jiang & Chen, 2024). As an external factor, entertainment links SMM stimuli to consumer responses, boosting engagement, eliciting positive emotions, and ultimately influencing purchase intentions (Zeqiri et al., 2025). Hence, the hypothesis has formed:

H12: Entertainment positively mediates the impact of SMM on purchase intention.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

Methodology

Sample and Population

The target population for this study comprises consumers of Pakistani fashion brands in Karachi, Pakistan. A total of 214 valid responses were collected, following SEM guidelines for determining an appropriate sample size (Kline, 2023). The study employed a simple random sampling technique to ensure unbiased selection and representativeness, targeting consumers active on social media platforms and influenced by online advertisements (Saunders et al., 2009).

Measures

SMM for SMEs was assessed using five items adapted from Kim and Ko (2012) on a five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree), with Cronbach's alpha above 0.85. Trust was measured with four items from Gefen (2000), evaluating confidence in content reliability and source honesty. Perceived value used items from Sweeney and Soutar (2001), while consumer purchase action was assessed with five items from Harrigan et al. (2018). All constructs showed high reliability, with Cronbach's alpha exceeding 0.80.

Data Collection

The study used a survey method with online questionnaires via Google Forms to collect data. This approach allowed efficient, cost-effective, and standardized data collection from digitally active consumers. Online surveys

ensured wide reach, anonymity, and accurate responses, making them suitable for analyzing relationships between social media marketing, trust, brand awareness, perceived value, entertainment, and purchase intention (Groves et al., 2011).

Data Analysis

The quantitative data analysis method examined relationships among variables and tested hypotheses. Descriptive statistics analyzed demographics, while inferential techniques, including correlation, reliability (Cronbach's Alpha), and Structural Equation Modelling (SEM), validated the measurement and structural model. SEM enabled simultaneous assessment of construct relationships, ensuring accurate, objective, and valid evaluation of social media marketing's influence on consumer purchase actions (Hair et al., 2019a).

Results and Discussions

Measurement Model

The measurement model evaluates reliability and validity of constructs and their indicators. It makes each variable to be measured correctly. In the research process, it assisted in concluding that the survey questions were powerful to actualize some of the concepts and philosophies such as brand awareness, entertainment, purchase intention, perceived value, SMM factors and trust (Hair et al., 2019b). Table 1 provide the results of measurement model using PLS algorithm technique.

Table 1:

Measurement Model

Constructs	Items	Loadings	Prob.	VIF	Alpha	CR	AVE
Brand Awareness	BA3	0.887	0.000	2.125	0.850	0.909	0.769
	BA4	0.848	0.000	1.923			
	BA5	0.895	0.000	2.224			
Entertainment	EN1	0.844	0.000	2.050	0.881	0.918	0.737
	EN2	0.837	0.000	2.096			
	EN3	0.896	0.000	3.290			
	EN4	0.855	0.000	2.798			
Purchase Intention	PI1	0.833	0.000	1.686	0.777	0.870	0.691
	PI2	0.809	0.000	1.503			
	PI4	0.852	0.000	1.659			
Perceived Value	PV2	0.906	0.000	1.885	0.813	0.914	0.842
	PV3	0.929	0.000	1.885			
Social Media Marketing Factors	SM1	0.765	0.000	1.293	0.716	0.794	0.562
	SM2	0.712	0.000	1.266			
	SM4	0.770	0.000	1.155			
Trust	TR1	0.801	0.000	1.192	0.773	0.823	0.699
	TR2	0.870	0.000	1.192			

The above table showed that indicators have loadings higher than the recommended threshold of 0.70 with probability level and VIF below 5% (Hair et al., 2022; Hair et al., 2011) manifesting that indicators have substantial reliability for achieving construct validity. Moreover, constructs have alpha coefficient and composite reliability higher than the recommended thresholds of 0.70 and

0.80, respectively (Hair et al., 2019b), and therefore, construct reliability has been established. Lastly, the table showed that constructs have AVE coefficients higher than 0.50 (Hair et al., 2011, 2013), and thus, it manifested a substantial degree of convergence between indicators and constructs.

Discriminant Validity

Table 2 show the result of FLC for assessing discriminant validity using PLS algorithm.

Table 2:

Fornell-Larcker Criteria (FLC)

	BA	ENT	PI	PV	SMMF	TR
BA	0.877					
ENT	0.713	0.858				
PI	0.720	0.725	0.831			
PV	0.703	0.583	0.639	0.918		
SMMF	0.597	0.517	0.483	0.592	0.750	
TR	0.593	0.462	0.532	0.629	0.517	0.836

BA = Brand Awareness; ENT = Entertainment; PI = Purchase Intention; PV = Perceived Value; SMMF = Social Media Marketing Factors; TR =

Trust
The above table showed that diagonally bold values (i.e., square root of the AVE coefficients)

are higher than their respective correlation coefficients, providing that constructs have a higher degree of variance than their correlation with other constructs (Ab Hamid et al., 2017;

Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Therefore, constructs have a substantial degree of divergence; thus, discriminant validity using FLC has established.

Figure 2: PLS Algorithm using SmartPLS

Table 3 show the result of HTMT ratio for assessing discriminant validity using PLS algorithm.

Table 3:

Heterotrait - Monotrait (HTMT) Ratio

	BA	ENT	PI	PV	SMMF	TR
BA						
ENT	0.817					
PI	0.881	0.876				
PV	0.848	0.683	0.795			
SMMF	0.801	0.687	0.681	0.826		
TR	0.847	0.644	0.791	0.899	0.842	

BA = Brand Awareness; ENT = Entertainment; PI = Purchase Intention; PV = Perceived Value; SMMF = Social Media Marketing Factors; TR = Trust

Henseler et al. (2016); Henseler et al. (2015) recommended that the HTMT ratio between two latent constructs should be less than 0.90 in order to establish discriminant validity. The table shows that the highest HTMT ratio of

0.899 was found among TR and PV, implying that discriminant validity using HTMT ratio has achieved.

Table 4 show the result of crossloadings method for assessing discriminant validity using PLS algorithm.

Table 4:

Crossloadings

	BA	ENT	PI	PV	SMMF	TR
BA3	0.887	0.632	0.642	0.598	0.568	0.498
BA4	0.848	0.522	0.548	0.689	0.487	0.526

BA5	0.895	0.709	0.695	0.575	0.511	0.539
EN1	0.647	0.844	0.585	0.513	0.547	0.471
EN2	0.582	0.837	0.629	0.600	0.431	0.429
EN3	0.636	0.896	0.691	0.503	0.391	0.388
EN4	0.578	0.855	0.581	0.374	0.400	0.287
PI1	0.558	0.613	0.833	0.443	0.424	0.419
PI2	0.636	0.578	0.809	0.493	0.365	0.409
PI4	0.601	0.618	0.852	0.643	0.416	0.493
PV2	0.601	0.506	0.567	0.906	0.477	0.545
PV3	0.684	0.560	0.604	0.929	0.601	0.606
SM1	0.416	0.420	0.321	0.437	0.765	0.350
SM2	0.337	0.291	0.292	0.426	0.712	0.325
SM4	0.558	0.433	0.451	0.465	0.770	0.467
TR1	0.453	0.361	0.419	0.386	0.368	0.801
TR2	0.534	0.409	0.469	0.645	0.487	0.870

BA = Brand Awareness; ENT = Entertainment; PI = Purchase Intention; PV = Perceived Value; SMMF = Social Media Marketing Factors; TR = Trust

The above table showed that indicators have higher loadings in their constructs compared to their crossloadings in other constructs. This showed that constructs shared higher variance in their constructs than in other constructs (Ab

Hamid et al., 2017; Cheung & Wang, 2017) manifesting that constructs have substantial divergence from other constructs establishing discriminant validity using crossloadings. Predictive Power and Relevance

Table 5 shows the predictive power of the endogenous constructs using PLS algorithm.

Table 5:
Predictive Power and Relevance

	R-Square	Q-Square
Brand Awareness	0.356	0.512
Entertainment	0.267	0.547
Purchase Intention	0.633	0.374
Perceived value	0.350	0.447
Trust	0.267	0.147

R² score for purchase intention is 63.3 percent and the Q² value is 37.4 percent, purchase intention demonstrates high predictive strength and moderate predictive relevance, indicating that the model variables contribute substantially to its explained variance. Brand awareness shows significant predictive relevance, R² of 35.6% and Q² of 51.2%, which indicates strong predictive relevance and a moderate level of variance explained. Likewise, perceived value has a moderate predictive power as the R² and Q² values are 35.0% and 44.7% respectively, signifying a

good level of predictive relevance. Entertainment shows modest predictive power, with an R² of 26.7 percent and a Q² of 54.7 percent, demonstrating comparatively higher relevance in prediction. In contrast, trust reveals lower predictive strength, as its R² value of 26.7 percent and Q² of 14.7 percent suggest only limited predictive relevance. Overall, the constructs perform the role of predicting the purchase intentions and related outcomes within the structural model (Chin, 1998; Cohen, 1988, 1992).

Structural Model

The structural model helps to understand the relationship between variables as per hypothesized relationship between them. In direct-effect analysis, the model analyzes the

relationship between independent and dependent variables while the specific indirect-effect analysis helps to determine the impact of independent variable on outcome variable through a mediator (Hair et al., 2020).

Table 6 provide the result of direct-effect analysis for hypothesis testing based on the PLS algorithm analysis.

Table 6:
Direct-Effect Analysis

	Estimate	Std. Dev.	t-Statistics	Prob.	Decision
BA -> PI	0.273	0.084	3.274	0.001	Supported
ENT -> PI	0.397	0.071	5.589	0.000	Supported
PV -> PI	0.162	0.058	2.780	0.005	Supported
SMMF -> BA	0.597	0.050	11.915	0.000	Supported
SMMF -> ENT	0.517	0.058	8.954	0.000	Supported
SMMF -> PV	0.592	0.045	13.228	0.000	Supported
SMMF -> TR	0.517	0.051	10.064	0.000	Supported
TR -> PI	0.084	0.056	1.510	0.131	Not Supported

BA = Brand Awareness; ENT = Entertainment; PI = Purchase Intention; PV = Perceived Value; SMMF = Social Media Marketing Factors; TR = Trust

The result showed that BA ($\beta = 0.273$; $p < 0.05$) has a positive and significant effect on PI. Similarly, ENT ($\beta = 0.397$; $p < 0.05$) has a positive and significant effect on PI. PV ($\beta = 0.162$; $p < 0.05$) has a positive and significant effect on PI. Additionally, SMMF ($\beta = 0.597$; $p < 0.05$) has a positive and significant effect on BA. SMMF ($\beta = 0.517$; $p < 0.05$) has a positive

and significant effect on ENT. Also, SMMF ($\beta = 0.592$; $p < 0.05$) has a positive and significant effect on PV. SMMF ($\beta = 0.517$; $p < 0.05$) has a positive and significant effect on TR. In addition, TR ($\beta = 0.084$; $p < 0.05$) has a positive and significant effect on PI.

Table 7 provide the result of specific indirect-effect analysis for hypothesis testing based on the PLS algorithm analysis.

Table 7:
Specific Indirect-Effect Analysis

	Estimate	Std. Dev.	t-Statistics	Prob.	Decision
SMMF -> TR -> PI	0.043	0.029	1.487	0.137	Not Supported
SMMF -> PV -> PI	0.096	0.035	2.769	0.006	Supported
SMMF -> ENT -> PI	0.205	0.044	4.694	0.000	Supported
SMMF -> BA -> PI	0.163	0.052	3.110	0.002	Supported

BA = Brand Awareness; ENT = Entertainment; PI = Purchase Intention; PV = Perceived Value; SMMF = Social Media Marketing Factors; TR = Trust

The result showed that TR ($\beta = 0.043$; $p > 0.05$) has positively insignificant mediates between SMMF and PI. PV ($\beta = 0.096$; $p < 0.05$) has positively significant mediates between SMMF and PI. ENT ($\beta = 0.205$; $p <$

0.05) has positively significant mediates between SMMF and PI. Also, BA ($\beta = 0.163$; $p < 0.05$) has positively significant mediates between SMMF and PI.

Figure 3: PLS Bootstrapping using SmartPLS

Discussions

The result showed that BA has positively significant effects on PI. This result is supported with Shahid et al. (2017), who explained that brand awareness positively shaped purchase intention, because consumers are more likely to choose brands that they recognize and remember easily. Understanding reduces perceived risk, improves confidence and gives the known brand the ability to be rated better by others. Similarly, Krisnawan and Jatra (2021) supported this result and stated that if consumers are trusting and valued brands, they will want to purchase because there is a stronger confidence and perceived value in the product.

The study found that ENT has positively significant effects on PI. This outcome is consistent with Lu et al. (2022), who acknowledged that entertainment has a positive effect on purchase intention as it is entertaining with respect to its content and allows its audience to experience the brand in a way that creates a memorable brand experience. It's more enjoyable for the users when the content is entertaining or has emotional gratifications; consumers feel more positive towards the brand and they are more willing to purchase the brand. Moreover, Majeed et al. (2021) confirmed these results and they concluded entertaining content do engage users and create emotional bonding

with brand. This positive affect enhances brand attitudes and lowers psychological barriers to buying.

The result indicated that PV significantly and positively influenced PI. This result is supported with Gan and Wang (2017), that the perception of value has a positive impact on the intention to purchase, as consumers tend to buy products that provide higher benefits in relation to its cost. When the value is obvious and persuasive, the consumer is more confident that he is making a good decision and is more likely to purchase. Likewise, Salehzadeh and Pool (2017) agreed with this finding and added that a high perceived value also delivers superior value and confidence to customers; these customers become more confident that the product is suitable for them.

The findings revealed that SMMF positively and significantly influenced BA. This result is consistent with Zeqiri et al. (2025), who suggested that SMM has a positive effect on the brand awareness as the contents are relevant and interesting which makes it more visible on various platforms. When users are obsessed with posts, promotions, and features, they become more acquainted with the brand and the sense of trust and memory. Additionally, Monica and Bala (2014) supported the result and they mentioned that an effective social media marketing draws the users' attention through likes, posts, comments and

viral contents. These are essentially shares of the brand that not only promote it, but enable more people to access its information rapidly going viral and exponentially building more brand awareness.

The finding showed that SMMF has positively significant effects on ENT. This outcome is supported with Cheung et al. (2020), there is the impact of SMM on entertainment that was described because creative visuals, interactive feature, and attractive content formats lead users to have enjoyable experience. If advertising is infused with humor, storytelling or interactive media, marketers are more likely believe that their brand's content is entertaining to the audience. Furthermore, Abbas Naqvi et al. (2020) This result was also supported by and SMM enhances entertainment through dynamic features of short videos, such as polls, challenges, and live interaction. These functionality are aligned with the users' interest and participation, and make the content feel exciting and fun as an increment in perceived enjoyment.

The study found that SMMF has positively significant effects on PV. This result is supported with Ajina (2019), that the effect of SMM on the perceived value is positive since it enables the brands to emphasize the benefits of the product and the unique aspects of the products. Advertising, quality and functional benefits enable consumers to think more accurately and even cause them to have a higher level of appreciation about the value of the product in perception of value. Moreover, Chen and Lin (2019) supported and discussed that SMM increases trust and credibility through engaging content, influencer's opinions, and customer stories. This interaction leads consumers to believe the product is effective and dependable; it also enhances their perceived value and results in a more positive brand attitude.

This result is supported with Irshad et al. (2020), who explained that it is positive to see SMM practices exert positive influence on trust because brand messages reflect strong and transparent communication. Consumer confidence is reinforced with the authenticity of brand stories, updates and responses to customer queries. Likewise, Hanaysha (2022) supported this result and indicated that social

media activity, such as reviews, testimonials and endorsements, strengthens trust by bringing social proof. When consumers see positive interactions and endorsements from other users, consumers feel the brand is reliable and trustworthy and they are more likely to be engaged and decision makers, able to buy things.

The study showed that TR has positively significant effects on PI. This result is consistent with Ganguly et al. (2009), who demonstrated that high levels of trust strengthen consumer and brand emotional and psychological relationships. When consumers are confident about a brand's authenticity and honesty, they are more willing to be willing to invest in a purchase, and buying. Also, Meskaran et al. (2013) supported this result and stated that trust positively affects purchase intention because consumers will become more likely to buy from trustworthy and honest brands.

The result showed that TR has positively insignificant mediates between SMM factors and PI. This result is supported with Hanaysha (2022), who explained that trust may serve to be a little unlikely mediator between SMM and purchase intent if consumers do not perceive the content of social media content as entirely credible or reliable. Although exposure to SMM is a factor in buying intention, it is limited by the trustworthiness of brand that does not translate significantly to how purchase intentions are transformed. In addition, Dutta and Bhat (2016) supported this result and indicated that with consumers focusing more on entertainment, value or brand awareness, the mediating role of trust becomes diminished.

The finding showed that PV has positively significant mediates between SMM factors and PI. This outcome is supported with Bushara et al. (2023), who demonstrated that SMM practices include informative posts, promotions, and influencer endorsements so consumers perceive value in the product. This increased perceived value enhances their confidence and desire to purchase, adding to the positive impact of social media marketing on the purchase impulse. Also, Widodo and Maylina (2022) supported this result and explained that the perceived value mediates

between SMM factors and purchase intention, because it is a product's advantages, quality, and usefulness via SMM.

The finding showed that ENT has positively significant mediates between SMM factors and PI. This result is supported with Bilal et al. (2021), who explained that SMM that has interesting elements such as interactive videos, games or storytelling, enhances user experience and engages. This increased engagement enhances brand recognition and encourages customers to re-engage and spend more time on the brand to make purchases. Moreover, Cheung et al. (2020) supported this result and stated that entertainment positively facilitates SMM and purchase intent by influencing both the relationship between engaging and engaging content and the value of using this engagement, providing consumers a positive attitude toward the brand.

The study found that BA has positively significant mediates between SMM factors and PI. This result is supported with Huo and Filieri (2025), who explained that brand awareness helps to link social media marketing factors and purchase intentions based on the fact that effective SMM increases visibility and recognition of the brand. When consumers have familiarized themselves with a brand after they interact with them on social media, they are likely to trust it and consider purchasing their own product. Likewise, Maria et al. (2019) supported this result and stated that SMM strategies consisting of engaging content, promotions, and influencer collaborations reinforce the mental connection and recall of a brand through engaging content.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The study investigated the impact of social media marketing on consumer purchase intention of fashion brands in Pakistan, dwelling upon trust, brand awareness, perceived value and entertainment as mediator constructs. The study used SOR theory for theoretical underpinning. Additionally, the study used a quantitative methodology. The target population of the study have consumers of Pakistani fashion brands. A random selection method was used to choose the respondents for the study and used PLS-SEM to

assess a complex modeling framework. Data collection was accomplished through a rapid and comprehensive five-point Likert scale questionnaire as part of the survey method.

The study found that BA, ENT, PV have a positive and significant effect on PI. Additionally, SMMF has a positive and significant effect on BA, ENT, PV and TR. In addition, TR has a positive and significant effect on PI. However, TR has positively insignificant mediates between SMMF and PI. PV has positively significant mediates between SMMF and PI. ENT has positively significant mediates between SMMF and PI. Also, BA has positively significant mediates between SMMF and PI. It also underlines the need for strategies in online engagement, brand communication and interactive content to steer consumer decisions and for more effective brand audience relationships.

Theoretical Implications

This study has theoretical implications as it applies and expands SOR theory to examine the impact of social media marketing by Pakistani fashion brands on purchase intentions. It addresses gaps by exploring trust, brand awareness, perceived value, and entertainment in shaping consumer purchase intentions (Abbas et al., 2021). The study extends SOR theory by illustrating how external marketing stimuli influence consumer perceptions, attitudes, and behavioral outcomes such as purchase intention. Findings offer practical guidance for designing effective social media campaigns to enhance engagement, brand identifiability, and trust. The research emphasizes the importance of interactive, fun, and valuable content and enriches scholarly literature, providing a foundation for further studies in Pakistan's fashion industry (Khan et al., 2021).

Recommendations

Drawing on the findings, several recommendations can be made for marketing managers of Pakistani fashion brands to enhance consumer purchase intentions through social media marketing. Managers should develop a strong, coherent social media presence to increase product familiarity and popularity, ensuring consistent visuals,

messages, and tone across platforms. Pre-scheduling content, planning seasonal campaigns, and collaborating with credible influencers can boost exposure and trust. Communicating product quality, originality, sustainability, and use-related benefits, alongside exclusive deals or user-generated content such as reviews and unboxing videos, reinforces authenticity and value.

Entertaining and interactive content, including short videos, live streams, quizzes, polls, storytelling, and challenges, maintains consumer interest and emotional engagement. Monitoring engagement metrics helps refine content and guide future campaigns. Building trust requires transparency, prompt responses, credible content, flexible return policies, and authentic influencer partnerships. Data-driven approaches, including tracking engagement, click-through rates, impressions, conversions, and A/B testing, allow managers to optimize campaigns. Implementing strategies that emphasize brand awareness, perceived value, entertainment, and trust can improve consumer attention, loyalty, and purchase intention, enhancing brand positioning and engagement while maintaining competitiveness in Pakistan's fashion industry.

Limitations and Future Research

The potential implications of this study were limited due to several constraints. It targeted only consumers of Pakistani fashion brands, so results may not generalize to other countries or cultures; future research could explore cross-cultural contexts. Quantitative methods like structured questionnaires cannot capture deeper consumer motivations or perceptions; qualitative approaches such as interviews could provide richer insights. The cross-sectional design limited understanding of long-term effects. Future studies could use longitudinal research and include additional mediators or moderators, like social pressure or brand loyalty, to better understand how SMM influences purchase intention.

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